

Encapsulated Papillary Carcinoma of Breast: Single case study

Dr Rishabh Chotrani¹, Dr Jyoti Priyadarshini Shrivastava², Dr Shilpi Sikarwar³,

Dr Sourabh Shrivastava⁴, Dr Rajesh Gaur⁵

1-PG Resident, 2-Professor, 3-Associate Professor, 4-Assistant Professor, 5-Professor & HOD
Department of Pathology, GRMC Gwalior, M.P.

Abstract: Encapsulated papillary carcinoma is considered as a variant of Ductal Carcinoma In-Situ (DCIS), due to indolent behavior and excellent prognosis. It is an expansile papillary tumor with low or intermediate grade nuclei, occurring in postmenopausal woman. This report documents the case of a 70-year-old female who was diagnosed as an Encapsulated Papillary Carcinoma of Breast in histopathological examination.

Introduction:

Papillary lesions of the breast are a distinct histopathological entity with varying clinical, histological, radiological features and malignant potential. The spectrum of papillary neoplasms of the breast as listed by the WHO classification of tumors (5th edition), namely Intra Ductal Papilloma, Papillary Ductal Carcinoma In-Situ, Encapsulated Papillary Carcinoma, Solid-Papillary Carcinoma, and Invasive Papillary Carcinoma (IPC).^[1]

Less than 2% of breast carcinomas are papillary carcinomas and only a proportion of these are encapsulated papillary carcinomas, which are rare in males^[2]

Grossly it is a well-circumscribed papillary tumor surrounded by a thick fibrous capsule. Centrally located and often presents a breast mass with or without bloody nipple discharge.^[3]

Microscopically^[3]:

- The fibrovascular cores are delicate and are surmounted by a monotonous proliferation of atypical epithelial cells that may, in addition to the papillary pattern, have areas of solid or cribriform architecture.
- As with papillary DCIS, there is an absence of myoepithelial cells along the fibrovascular cores, but in contradistinction to the DCIS, there is also an absence of myoepithelial cells at the periphery of most encapsulated papillary carcinomas^[4-6], raising the possibility that these tumors may be low-grade invasive carcinomas rather than in situ lesions^[7,8].

The observed lack of a myoepithelial cell layer, on haematoxylin-and-eosin-stained sections as well as with immunohistochemistry for a variety of myoepithelial cell markers, runs counter to our current understanding of an in-situ lesion.

This is a phenomenon that has only recently been documented in the literature, but it raises the possibility that encapsulated papillary carcinomas may represent a minimally invasive, low-grade, or indolent form of invasive carcinoma rather than an in-situ lesion.

Further evidence of the potential invasive nature of encapsulated papillary carcinoma is the rare occurrence of axillary lymph node metastases, even in the absence of conventional invasive carcinoma.^[9]

Case report: A 70-year-old female came to our hospital with a swelling in her right breast. She had the swelling for last 5 years but fell recently and took an injury to the breast resulting in increasing size of the swelling. There was no axillary swelling. The patient was sent for FNAC but was non-diagnostic and a total right mastectomy was done.

The mastectomy specimen measured 15x11x5cm with overlying skin ulcerated and nipple retracted.

Fig 1 Grossing Images

Fig 1.1 Total mastectomy specimen, Anterior view.

Fig 1.2 Total mastectomy specimen, Posterior view.

Fig 1.3 On cutting mastectomy specimen, blood was coming out.

Fig 1.4 Organized Blood with necrosed tissue

Fig 1.5 Intacystic growth seen after cleaning the blood

Fig 2 Microscopic Pictures

Fig 2.1 Histological section shows delicate papillary fronds lined by cuboidal to columnar epithelial cells. Individual cells show mild to moderate nuclear atypia. H&E stain 100x

Fig 2.2 Histological section shows a clear view of ductal epithelia cells arranged in papillae pattern. H&E stain 400x

Fig 2.3 Histological section shows cribriform architecture. H&E stain 400x

Fig 2.4 Histological section shows cribriform architecture. H&E stain 400x

Fig 2.6 Histological section shows tissue lined by thick fibrous capsule. The underlying tissue shows ductal epithelial cells forming true papillae having fibrovascular core. However, capsule is devoid of invasion. H&E stain 400x

Result:

On cutting the mastectomy specimen, dark red blood came out of the incision. The breast appeared to have a cavity filled with blood and necrosed material, which on removing showed a papillary growth measuring 3x2x0.8cm. The growth was not invading and was sitting on a fibrous capsule. The whole cavity's outline was intact. No secondary growth was seen. On microscopy the Histologic type was found out to be Encapsulated papillary carcinoma without invasive carcinoma.

Immunohistochemistry was done: ER: Positive, PR: Positive, HER2/neu: Negative and Ki 67%: Low.

Discussion:

It is important to evaluate areas of unequivocal conventional invasive carcinoma, as this will influence how the patient is staged and treated.

This can be more challenging than might be imagined as most patients have undergone a core needle biopsy procedure with the consequent displacement of epithelial nests into the biopsy site and fibrous capsule. Therefore, it is prudent to restrict diagnosis of associated invasive carcinoma to focus clearly away from the biopsy site.

As far as tumor staging, it is the recommendation of the WHO Working Group that encapsulated papillary carcinomas be staged and managed as in situ lesions (Tis); any associated microinvasive or invasive carcinoma should be reported and staged according to the size of the largest focus of conventional invasive carcinoma.^[7]

Encapsulated papillary carcinomas are typically ER and PR positive and HER2 negative.

Most encapsulated papillary carcinomas have low or intermediate grade nuclei and behave in an indolent manner; however, there are rare cases of encapsulated papillary carcinoma that have high grade nuclei and brisk mitotic rate.^[10]

Recent data indicate that the tumors, which represent approximately 3% of encapsulated papillary carcinomas, behave in a more aggressive manner (high grade cytologic atypia and increased mitotic activity) and as such should be staged and managed as conventional invasive carcinoma.^[10] Prognosis is better for Low and intermediate grade Encapsulated Papillary Carcinoma without conventional invasive carcinoma has similar clinical behaviour to ductal carcinoma in situ (DCIS), staged as DCIS in the absence of invasive carcinoma^[11]. 95% of cases have 10-year survival in the absence of associated invasive carcinoma. Local recurrence is possible in 7% of cases. Lymph node metastases are rare, only in 3% of cases. If invasion beyond the capsule is present, it is staged based on the size of the invasive component, not the size of the EPC. Patients with invasive carcinomas arising from EPCs may have a better prognosis compared to age and stage matched conventional invasive carcinomas. However High-grade carcinoma with EPC features^[12]. These have Low incidence (3% of EPC). They have similar clinical behaviour to invasive carcinoma with greater propensity of lymphovascular invasion and lymph node metastases when compared to low and intermediate grade EPC. They are best classified as high-grade invasive breast carcinoma with features of EPC and staged as an invasive carcinoma. Current modalities of treatment include Surgical excision alone for in situ carcinoma. Aggressive cancer is treated as invasive carcinoma.

Conclusion:

Encapsulated papillary carcinoma (EPC) is a rare malignant papillary breast tumor that, despite a lack of distinct myoepithelial layer, is considered an in-situ carcinoma unless associated with a frank invasive component. It is considered as a variant of DCIS, it has indolent behaviour and a good prognosis. It rarely shows lymph node involvement or metastasis. Prognosis is good with total surgical resection.

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